

SLANG AS A BASE OF YOUTHS LANGUAGE

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Abstract: Slangs are one of the most-used language variations. The bigger proportion of people who use slangs are youths. This research deals with slang and its interpretations. The study also counts reasons why nowadays teenagers choose colloquialisms for expression thoughts and feelings.

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Our language is loaded with various types of vocabulary. There are so many "new things" that can be nonunderstandable for elder people. The most common one is slangs. It may seem easier to express our feelings and emotions by using informal words. Some people find it as unpolite way of expression oneself. What is slang by itself? Slang, according to Oxford vocabulary, is very informal words used more in spoken language than in written language. Slangs are restricted to particular context and even a group of people. Take a look at the history of "new words".

The term “slang” was first recognized by lexicographer Francis Grose in 1785. He defined it as “cant” or “vulgar” language. Interestingly enough, slang actually appeared before it was labeled as such, under the name of Thieves’ Cant. This secret cryptic language – now fallen into disuse – was created in 1600 England by thieves, tramps, criminals and vagabonds as a way of excluding or confusing a particular group of people, namely the authorities.

For decades, the word “slang” referred to the vocabulary of “low” or “disreputable” people. By the early nineteenth century, it was no longer exclusively associated with such groups, but continued to be applied to usages below the level of standard educated speech.

Slang is often short-lived: what’s new and exciting for one generation is soon old-fashioned for the next. Some former slang words have even been accepted into the standard language, therefore losing part of their eccentricity. Such is the case for

the 1930 slang word “swell” or the word “gnarly”, a former Australian surfer slang term used to describe dangerous waves. Much American slang has gone mainstream after being invented by African Americans. And slang terms are often used to forge bonds in subcultures, as well as in-crowds and youth. The history of a word like cool, for one, is not just about a gap between generations but representation and appropriation.

Slang, as linguist and lexicographer Ben Zimmer explains, allows “cultural groups to create their own kind of territory through language.” When a word seeps beyond the original group who uses it to signal shared attitudes, that can be just as hurtful for the old speakers as it is exciting for the new ones. The earliest known slang was used among criminal groups centuries ago, as a way to keep their communication from being understood by authorities. It has always been used, on some level, to say “we are the marginal folk,” as he puts it. Slang can be mean and uncaring and disgusting. It can also bind people and define the boundaries of the gang. “It confirms that we’re together and it confirms that you’re not one of us.”

Nowadays, slangs are the main language in which teen-agers make conversations. They use slangs as their own way to differentiate among others.

So for most people slang is language too. It is a language of glitters and sparkles, of words that dazzle, die and turn to ash within a month, so protean that even its most practiced users are unsure of what it means at any given time, for meaning is its least conspicuous element.

Like all slang, that of the teen-agers is language on a certain level, below both standard , formal English and colloquial speech, but above vulgarisms and illiterate usages. But it is language, and if part of the job of English teacher today is to assist his students to awareness of the nature and purpose of language, then an illuminating investigation of slang may have a legitimate place within the classroom .

The purpose of language is communication , language implies a certain type of social relationship between the speaker and his audience , language is influenced by time, by place, and by the gender of the speaker. Socially, temporally, geographically, and educationally language characterizes its speaker. Slang is an excellent vehicle for teaching all of these concepts. Practically speaking, the utilisation of slang to teach basic concepts about language has one tremendous advantage: Slang is language in which teenagers are demonstrably interested.

Language variation, slang, is one of the recently language uses in mostly teenager interaction. They use this language variation in having various types and reasons. Recently, an experiment was carried out on determining the types of slangs.

The study found that the types of slang language used in teenager interaction showed various results in each type. The first highest result was acronym with total 33 words or 37.93%. Then, the second was clipping with the total 25 words or 28.75%. Next, the third was fresh and creative with the total 16 words or 18.39%. After that, the fourth was compounding with the total eight words or 9.19%, and the lowest was imitative with the total five or 5.74%. In line with the result of slang language used types, the result of teenagers' reason in using slang on their interaction also showed impressive results. There were seven reasons of why teenagers were using slang language in their interaction. The first highest result was the reason of to enrich the language by inventing new words with the total 15 frequencies or 17.85%. Then, the reason was to induce either friendliness with the total 14 frequencies or 16.70%. Next, the reason was to be different and for easing of social intercourse with the total 13 or 15.47%. The reasons of to be different and for easing of social intercourse had the same frequencies and percentage in this result. After that, the reason was to reduce seriousness of a conversation with the total 11 frequencies or 13.09%. Next, the reason was just for fun of the thing with the total 10 frequencies or 11.90%, and the last reason was for delights in virtuosity with the total eight frequencies or 9.52%.

The study of word origins enjoyed considerable popularity in the past, and etymologies, a traditional component of a dictionary entry, were often hotly debated, even though 'the amateurs who, as late as 1900, filled the pages of popular journals with their conjectures on word origin, had no idea that they should have used their time reading rather than writing'.

New borrowing words appeared by the development of world trade, the international tourism, cultural connections. The youth is an integral part of any society, irrespective of his intrinsic characteristics. It represents the social and demographic group united on certain signs: to age, the social status and social and psychological properties, and the youth culture is among the particularly complex phenomena. In our modern world using slangs among youths is a reason of being unaware of the history of country and society. Young people use this language variation as something modern, trend. Most people for whom using colloquialisms is normal do not know anything about history of language. In past, elite tried to use mostly the highest level words in language that were challenging to understand for low class people. Learned people spent money for education, learning languages and morals of high society. It was impossible to notice "new words" or slangs in their speech. That was the highlight of their society. So the slangs were the highlight of

low society. Poor or uneducated people used their own language for making conversations that were easy for them to understand. Their language was nonunderstandable for wealthy, educated people.

The youth culture is one of consequences of process of socialization in general and cultural in particular. Its social and psychological sources are in aspiration of youth in general and its certain representatives to consciousness, self-affirmation, self-expression and self-realization. These natural aspirations not always get necessary support. The main aspiration of youth subculture practically always is fixing of the most important for them of world outlook concepts of a bright expressional form, perhaps, unclear for the most people in society. Use of slang in the speech of teenagers gives it beauty and emotionality, according to young people. Teenagers use also English-speaking slang which sometimes is clear only to youth for expression of the thoughts.

For saving the pure content of our language we must avoid using slangs in our speech. Even without those "beautiful new words" we have tremendous amount of old words for expression thoughts. With pure old-aged words our speech is even more attractive and effective.

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